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Fabio Cabeccia, University of Cagliari, *fabio.cabeccia@unica.it*

Luigi Raffo, University of Cagliari, *raffo@unica.it*

Francesca Palumbo, University of Cagliari, *francesca.palumbo@unica.it*

Claudio Rubattu, University of Sassari, *crubattu@uniss.it*

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AI-Guided DSE of GEMM Kernels for Vision Transformers on FPGA-Based Edge Platforms

Fabio Cabeccia¹, Luigi Raffo¹[0000-0001-9683-009X], Francesca Palumbo¹[0000-0002-7070-2409], and Claudio Rubattu²[0000-0002-1265-4816]

¹ University of Cagliari, Cagliari 09123, Italy
fabio.cabeccia@unica.it, raffo@unica.it, francesca.palumbo@unica.it

² University of Sassari, Sassari, 07100 Italy
crubattu@uniss.it

Abstract. Vision Transformers (ViTs) have recently demonstrated superior accuracy compared to Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) in several computer vision tasks. Nevertheless, their deployment on resource-constrained edge devices remains challenging due to their high computational and memory demands. This work investigates the feasibility of Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA)-based acceleration of General Matrix Multiplication (GEMM) layers in ViTs, where they represent the dominant computational workload, by means of a structured and parametric Design Space Exploration (DSE) methodology. These kernels are implemented using AMD Vitis HLS and optimized by varying key parameters (e.g., unrolling, pipelining, data precision, etc.). In parallel, the feasibility of representative ViT-related GEMM workloads, each defined by different matrix sizes and layer composition, is evaluated in terms of estimated FPGA resource usage and latency. The resulting hardware configurations are evaluated on two target FPGA platforms with different resource profiles: the AMD Kria KV260, representative of edge-oriented devices, and the more resource-rich AMD ZCU102. The proposed DSE aims to untangle the large number of possible configurations and their complex trade-offs among resource usage, latency, and numerical precision. To address this challenge, an Artificial Intelligence (AI)-based predictive search method is proposed to identify the most suitable implementation that minimizes latency while meeting target precision settings and resource constraints. The proposed approach achieves prediction errors comparable to state-of-the-art methods and shows the feasibility limits of deploying ViT-related GEMM workloads on FPGA-based edge devices.

Keywords: Vision Transformers · FPGA · AMD Vitis HLS · Design Space Exploration · GEMM.

1 Introduction

In recent years, the rapid proliferation of edge computing has significantly reshaped the landscape of computer vision applications. Modern edge scenarios,

such as smart cameras, autonomous robots, industrial inspection systems, and intelligent sensing platforms, increasingly require the execution of complex vision pipelines directly on embedded devices, close to where data are generated [30]. This paradigm shift is mainly driven by stringent constraints on latency, bandwidth, privacy, and reliability, which often make cloud-based processing impractical or undesirable. As a consequence, AI techniques for computer vision are progressively migrating from centralized data centers to the edge, where inference must be performed under tight power, memory, and computational constraints typical of embedded systems [27]. Achieving high inference accuracy while maintaining low latency and energy efficiency thus represents a fundamental challenge for edge-oriented AI systems [9].

From an algorithmic perspective, the evolution of computer vision models has moved beyond traditional CNNs, which have long dominated the field. Although CNNs remain widely adopted due to their favorable trade-off between accuracy and computational cost, recent advances have introduced alternative architectures capable of capturing richer global dependencies in visual data. Among these, ViTs have emerged as a particularly promising solution, demonstrating superior accuracy and remarkable flexibility across a wide range of vision tasks [22]. By relying on self-attention mechanisms rather than convolutional operations, ViTs are able to model long-range interactions more effectively and to scale more naturally with model size and data complexity. However, these advantages come at the cost of significantly increased computational and memory demands, which pose substantial obstacles to their deployment on resource-constrained edge devices. On the hardware side, only a limited set of edge platforms is currently capable of supporting the inference of such computationally intensive models. State-of-the-art edge systems are often built around heterogeneous architectures that combine general-purpose processing units, such as Central Processing Units (CPUs), with specialized accelerators tailored for high-throughput and energy-efficient execution of AI workloads [25]. CPUs are essential for running operating systems, managing system-level tasks, and orchestrating applications, often through virtualization or container-based frameworks [23]. At the same time, acceleration platforms such as Graphics Processing Units (GPUs) and FPGAs are employed to offload and speed up computationally demanding kernels, including neural network inference. Representative examples include GPU-based platforms like the NVIDIA Jetson Orin family [20], and FPGA-based solutions such as the AMD Zynq Ultrascale+ (ZU+) family [1], which integrate programmable logic with embedded processors in a single System on a Chip (SoC).

Despite the growing interest in ViTs, their adoption on edge platforms remains limited, especially when compared to CNN-based solutions [24]. Most existing deployments of ViTs are still confined to high-end GPUs or cloud infrastructures, where computational resources and memory bandwidth are abundant. FPGA-based edge platforms, while offering compelling advantages in terms of energy efficiency, parallelism, and hardware-level customization, have seen only a small number of ViT implementations to date [28, 6]. This is mainly due to

the intrinsic complexity of ViT architectures, which involve large matrix multiplications, attention mechanisms, and substantial memory traffic, all of which complicate efficient mapping onto FPGA fabrics. As a result, an open question remains as to whether ViTs can be effectively implemented on edge-class FPGAs, and whether FPGA-optimized ViT implementations can retain the accuracy benefits that make these models attractive in the first place, or whether more conventional CNN-based approaches remain the preferable choice in such constrained environments, even in the presence of flexible functionalities [16].

Motivated by these research questions, this work aims to investigate the feasibility of GEMM-centric ViT acceleration on FPGA-based edge platforms by analyzing the design trade-offs involved in mapping the GEMM layers, which dominate the execution time of modern ViTs [14], onto FPGAs. Non-GEMM operations, such as *Softmax*, *GELU*, *LayerNorm*, and *tensor reshaping* are left for future work and may introduce additional latency or resources overhead in a full, end-to-end implementation. Therefore, the central question addressed in this study is whether it is possible to automatically identify hardware configurations for representative ViT GEMM workloads that are resource-efficient and capable of meeting the latency requirements of edge applications under limited FPGA resources. To this end, a set of configurations derived from real ViT architectures is evaluated on two representative devices from the AMD ZU+ family: the AMD Kria KV260 [3], which targets edge-oriented applications with relatively constrained FPGA resources, and the AMD ZCU102 [2], which is used as a higher-capacity reference platform within the same family. By considering these two targets, the proposed GEMM-oriented exploration methodology can be assessed across different FPGA resource budgets. The contributions of this paper are as follows.

1. First, two datasets are introduced for the exploration of GEMM-centric ViT acceleration on FPGAs. The first one covers GEMM kernels, synthesized on AMD Vitis HLS with different optimizations, such as loop unrolling, pipelining, tiling, and bit-width selection. The second captures representative ViT-related GEMM workloads derived from real architectures, varying in terms of matrix sizes, layer compositions, and attention-related configurations.
2. Second, two predictors built on the aforementioned datasets have been trained to estimate the key metrics of the hardware configurations before hardware synthesis: one targeting latency and the other FPGA resource usage.
3. Third, a systematic feasibility analysis has been conducted to select the optimal hardware configuration for representative ViT GEMM workloads that minimize latency while satisfying platform resource constraints. This analysis is required to verify whether a given workload can be successfully mapped onto the target FPGA devices while satisfying platform resource constraints under the selected precision settings.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the proposed methodology, including dataset generation, hardware synthesis process, and the AI-driven search strategy. Finally, Section 4 summarizes the main findings of this work, and outlines limitations and future work.

2 Methodology

This section presents a modular AI-based search methodology capable of predicting not only performance metrics but also the physical implementability of High-Level Synthesis (HLS) designs prior to synthesis. As illustrated in Figure 1, the proposed methodology comprises three stages, which are discussed in details in the following sections.

Figure 1: Overview of the three-stage AI-based methodology.

2.1 Data Generation

Parameter	Values	Description
m	64 – 2048	rows of first matrix
k	64 – 2048	shared matrices dimension
n	64 – 2048	columns of second matrix
T_m, T_n, T_k	32, 64, 128	tile size
U_m	4, 8, 16, 32	unroll factor over m loop
Bit Width	4, 8, 16	precision level (bits)

Table 1: GEMM kernel parameters.

The prediction of hardware performance metrics from HLS-derived data is performed by a Machine Learning (ML) model, thus the data generation procedure is critical for achieving reasonable performance. Datasets have been based on the analysis of HLS implementations of both general GEMM kernels and

ViT-specific GEMM workloads. To this aim, the proposed methodology starts from the *HLS design* of a kernel parameterized by matrix sizes, tiling and unroll factors, and bit-width. The loop unroll across the n dimension is not reported since it depends chosen bit width and it is not directly set by a targeted parameter. Table 1 lists the parameters paired with their respective domain. Once the kernel has been configured, the next step consists of a *HLS synthesis* with Vitis HLS. This tool provides an estimation of resource usage and latency, which serve as the targets of the dataset generated through multiple kernel configurations and the corresponding synthesis processes, enabling efficient *data entry*.

2.2 Hardware Predictive Model

In the proposed methodology, each hardware configuration, corresponding to a row of the dataset, is a vector $h \in \mathbb{R}^f$, with f number of features. Specifically, the set of features is a combination of implementation parameters, as defined in Section 2.1, and derived domain-aware features capturing tile geometry, loop structure, memory footprint, and parallelism characteristics has been added. Notably, compute density and padding waste are also included. The former is defined as the ratio of arithmetic operations to data volume per tile, and serves as a measure for arithmetic intensity in the Roofline model [29], indicating whether a configuration is compute-bound or memory-bound. The latter arises from partial tiles at matrix boundaries when dimensions are not evenly divisible by tile sizes, a well-known overhead in tiled computations [13, 26].

The extended dataset is used for training predictive models of latency (in clock cycles) and hardware resource usage, including Look-Up Tables (LUTs), Flip Flops (FFs), Block Random Access Memories (BRAMs), and Digital Signal Processors (DSPs) Formally, given the set of possible hardware configurations \mathcal{H} , the goal is to build a predictor $\mathcal{M} : \mathcal{H} \rightarrow (\mathbb{N}^k, \mathbb{N})$ that maps a hardware configuration $h \in \mathcal{H}$ to a pair resources-latency $y = (y_R, y_L)$, where $y_R \in \mathbb{N}^k$ is the resource vector of size $k = 4$, while $y_L \in \mathbb{N}$ is the scalar latency. Furthermore, ablation studies and model-selection experiments comparing linear models and tree-based ensembles have been conducted, leading to the adoption of gradient-boosted decision trees [8], a non-linear ensemble method offering several advantages for the prediction task: (1) it naturally captures complex, non-additive interactions among heterogeneous design parameters without requiring explicit feature engineering; (2) it is robust to mixed feature types (continuous, discrete, categorical) and varying scales, eliminating the need for extensive normalization; (3) it delivers strong out-of-the-box performance with modest hyperparameter tuning; and (4) it provides interpretable feature-importance diagnostics that offer insights into which design parameters most influence resource utilization and latency.

In conclusion, considering that resource counts (LUTs, FFs, BRAMs, and DSPs) and latency cycles exhibit distinct statistical distributions and serve different roles in the downstream optimization, two specialized predictors need to be trained: one for the resource vector $y_R \in \mathbb{N}^k$, called \mathcal{M}_R , and one for the

latency scalar $y_L \in \mathbb{N}$, called \mathcal{M}_L . This separation enables target-specific pre-processing and regularization, improving prediction error and interpretability compared to a single multi-output model [5].

2.3 Resource-Constrained Feasibility Search

Given the two trained predictors, \mathcal{M}_L for the latency and \mathcal{M}_R for the resources, the final stage determines an optimal configuration that minimizes latency while strictly respecting hardware resource constraints. The optimization is formulated as a *Multidimensional Multiple-Choice Knapsack Problem (MMKP)* [18] as follows. Consider a neural network with L layers, each corresponding to a matrix multiplication. For each layer i , a set of configurations $\mathcal{H}_i = \{h_{i,1}, \dots, h_{i,|\mathcal{H}_i|}\}$, with $\mathcal{H}_i \subseteq \mathcal{H}$, is generated, where each candidate $h_{i,j}$ is characterized by a predicted latency $y_L(h_{i,j}) \in \mathbb{N}$ and a resource vector $y_R(h_{i,j}) \in \mathbb{N}^4$, representing LUT, FF, BRAM, and DSP usage. The objective is to select exactly one configuration per layer such that total latency is minimized and the aggregate resource usage does not exceed the platform capacity \mathbf{R}_{\max} , or more formally: $\min_{h_i} \sum_{i=1}^N \text{lat}(h_i)$ s.t. $\sum_{i=1}^N \mathbf{r}(h_i) \leq \mathbf{R}_{\max}$, $h_i \in \mathcal{H}_i$. Note that the solver will always prefer the solution with higher bit width.

Although MMKP is NP-hard in general, the sequential structure of neural network layers enables efficient solving via A* search [10]. The *optimal search tree* is constructed such that each depth corresponds to a layer, and the heuristic estimates the minimum achievable latency for remaining layers. This approach guarantees feasibility, since every returned solution satisfies all resource constraints.

3 Assessment

The proposed methodology is evaluated on two aspects: (1) the prediction error of the resource and latency models across the hardware configuration search space, and (2) the effectiveness of the feasibility solver in identifying deployable configurations under strict resource constraints.

3.1 Experimental Setup

Predictors Evaluation The resource predictor \mathcal{M}_R and latency predictor \mathcal{M}_L are assessed using the dataset described in Section 2.1, comprising 2000 synthesis-based samples. Configurations defined by specific parameter values are randomly drawn from the bounded search space in Table 1. This sampling strategy ensures broad coverage across matrix sizes, tiling/unrolling choices and data precision levels. Therefore, the resulting matrix multiplication dataset contains diverse implementation configurations with their synthesis outcomes: resource usage, latency and related metrics. In particular, the dataset is partitioned into training (70%), validation (15%), and test (15%) splits. Prediction error is evaluated using complementary metrics on the held-out test set. The Coefficient

of Determination (R^2) measures the proportion of variance explained by the model, indicating overall predictive power (the higher the better). Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) quantifies the average relative deviation, enabling comparison across targets with different scales. Normalized Root Mean Squared Error (NRMSE) provides a scale-independent measure of absolute error magnitude, with sensitivity to outliers. Together, these metrics characterize both the correlation strength and the error distribution of the predictors [19, 4, 11].

Feasibility Solver Evaluation The feasibility solver is evaluated on various matrix multiplication configurations, either single executions or stacked. Additionally, some real-world workloads, extracted from real ViT attention mechanism, are used. Table 2 gives a quick-view of each tested configuration. Note that for the real case the focus the evaluation are the four projection layers ($Q, K, V, Output$) of the attention block, which dominate computational cost for typical ViT configurations where embedding dimension exceeds sequence length ($D > S$) [12]. To demonstrate the solver’s generality across resource budgets, two AMD ZU+ FPGA platforms are targeted. The former is the AMD Kria KV260, considered as an edge-oriented platform with constrained resources (117,120 LUTs, 234,240 FFs, 144 BRAM, 1248 DSPs), representing a case where feasibility is the primary challenge. The latter is the ZCU102, which has been considered as a high-performance evaluation platform (274,080 LUTs, 548,160 FFs, 912 BRAM, 2520 DSPs), representing a case where the solver must exploit available parallelism to minimize latency.

Benchmark	Layers	$(m \times k \times n)$	Objective
Scale_4096	1	$4096 \times 4096 \times 4096$	Max single-layer size
Depth_L	2-6	$256 \times 256 \times 256$	Layer count limits
		$256 \times 96 \times 96$	
MobileViT-XS [17]	3	$256 \times 96 \times 384$ $256 \times 384 \times 96$	MobileViT attention
ViT-Huge [12]	4	$197 \times 1280 \times 1280 (\times 4)$	ViT-Huge attention

Table 2: Benchmarks for feasibility solver evaluation.

3.2 Predictors Accuracy

Table 3 reports the prediction accuracy of the resource model \mathcal{M}_R and latency model \mathcal{M}_L on the held-out test set. Considering the small amount of data available, both models shows good prediction capacities. The resource predictor \mathcal{M}_R achieves strong performance across all targets, with $R^2 \geq 0.93$ indicating that the model explains the vast majority of variance in resource usage. MAPE values remain below 2.3% for all resource types, confirming low relative error suitable for

constraint checking. BRAM prediction achieves perfect accuracy, reflecting the deterministic relationship between tile dimensions and local buffer allocation. DSP exhibits the highest NRMSE (23.34%) despite low MAPE (1.12%), indicating the presence of occasional larger absolute errors; however, since MAPE remains small, these deviations are concentrated among low-usage configurations where absolute error has minimal impact on feasibility decisions. LUT and FF predictions show balanced metrics, indicating both strong correlation and well-bounded error distributions. The latency predictor \mathcal{M}_L achieves $R^2=0.99$, indicating strong correlation with actual synthesis results. The higher MAPE (10.43%) and NRMSE (17.85%) compared to resource targets are expected: latency spans three orders of magnitude and is influenced by scheduling decisions within the HLS tool that are not fully captured by the input feature. These results demonstrate that the proposed predictors provide sufficient accuracy for the downstream feasibility solver. Prior work on HLS quality-of-results prediction has established that MAPE below 10–15% enables effective design space exploration [5], while $R^2 > 0.90$ is considered strong predictive performance for FPGA accelerator modeling [7]. The latency predictor’s MAPE of 10.4% is also consistent with prior works [15].

Predictor	Target	R^2	MAPE [%]	NRMSE [%]
\mathcal{M}_R	LUT Usage	0.95	2.23	13.28
	FF Usage	0.97	1.58	10.50
	BRAM Usage	1.00	0.00	0.00
	DSP Usage	0.93	1.12	23.34
\mathcal{M}_L	Latency	0.99	10.43	17.85

Table 3: Final Predictor Performance on Held-Out Test Set.

3.3 Feasibility Solver Evaluation

The efficacy of the MMKP-based solver is evaluated on the benchmarks described in Table 2. Figure 2 illustrates how the solver adapts the generated configurations to the resource constraints of both target platforms. Importantly, with this specific hardware design, the solver is able to understand that the boundary depends on the number of concurrent layers rather than their individual dimensions: a single $4096 \times 4096 \times 4096$ multiplication is feasible, while six $256 \times 256 \times 256$ layers are not. The solver does not attempt to force infeasible designs; instead, it mathematically proves that no parameter combination satisfies the resource constraints. On the higher-capacity ZCU102, the solver finds that even six layers are not enough to saturate it, but DSPs start to behave like the bottleneck resource that may prevent deeper designs to be deployed.

Figure 2: Resource usage for each benchmark on both platforms.

Configuration Analysis Table 4 reports salient examples of the chosen configurations. For Depth_5L, the solver throttles unrolling on KV260 ($U=32 \rightarrow 16$) and reduces the tile sizes as the depth increases in order to respect BRAM limits; on the other hand, the ZCU102 sustains higher parallelism ($U=64$) and only shows a lower unroll in the last layer. In compute-bound tasks like Scale_4096 and ViT-Huge, the algorithm consistently converges to maximal tile dimensions (128^3) to exploit more DSP resources. MobileViT demonstrates the handling of irregular layer shapes with heterogeneous tiling, more evident on the smaller board. On the latency side, the difference between KV260 and ZCU102 is modest, and in the Scale_4096 case the reported latency, in cycles, is identical but this is expected: the two boards share the same architectural family and the chosen kernel configuration is also equal, causing the latency to be the same. A richer kernel library and a wider parameter range are expected to expose a larger board-dependent performance gap.

Data Precision The explored design space includes bit-widths from 4 to 16 bits, but only the configurations of the latter are showed since they are the most resource-demanding. Consequently, feasibility at 16 bits implies feasibility for the lower-precision configurations as well. While state-of-the-art FPGA accelerators often adopt aggressive 8-bit [31] or 16-bit [21] quantization to meet resource constraints, current results show that even 16-bit precision fits within the target edge platforms.

Board	Benchmark	Latency[cc]	Search Time[ms]	Configuration
KV260	Depth_5L	1.1×10^6	2520	$128 \times 128 \times 128 U=32$ $64 \times 64 \times 128 U=32 \times 3$ $64 \times 64 \times 128 U=16$
	Scale_4096	3.7×10^8	270	$128 \times 128 \times 128 U=128$
	MobileViT	3.7×10^5	500	$64 \times 64 \times 64 U=32$ $128 \times 64 \times 64 U=64$ $64 \times 64 \times 128 U=16$
ZCU102	ViT-Huge	1.1×10^7	970	$128 \times 128 \times 128 U=32 \times 4$
	Depth_5L	8.8×10^5	1990	$128 \times 128 \times 128 U=64 \times 4$ $128 \times 128 \times 128 U=32$
	Depth_6L	1.1×10^6	2730	$128 \times 128 \times 128 U=64 \times 4$ $128 \times 128 \times 128 U=32 \times 2$
	Scale_4096	3.7×10^8	300	$128 \times 128 \times 128 U=128$
	MobileViT	3.4×10^5	590	$128 \times 64 \times 64 U=64 \times 2$ $128 \times 64 \times 128 U=128$
	ViT-Huge	9.4×10^6	820	$128 \times 128 \times 128 U=64 \times 4$

Table 4: Latency is the total number of clock cycles (cc). Configuration: $T_m \times T_n \times T_k | U_m | \times l$ repeats layer.

4 Conclusions

This work has explored the feasibility of ViT-based inference on FPGA-based edge platforms through a structured and parametric DSE. The results highlight the importance of DSE in understanding the feasibility limits of GEMM-centric ViT acceleration at the edge, where FPGA resource constraints and inference latency are strongly interdependent. By modeling and exploring matrix multiplication kernels derived from multiple ViT structural configurations, the proposed approach enables a systematic analysis of trade-offs across heterogeneous platforms. The findings indicate that predictive AI-based exploration can identify viable configurations. Future work includes extending the proposed framework toward a more comprehensive DSE flow for FPGA-based edge platforms, by incorporating additional ViT operators beyond GEMM, validating selected configurations through implementation on physical devices, and leveraging a library of optimized parametric kernels together with a runtime decision mechanism to dynamically select the most suitable configuration based on device conditions, environmental requirements, or user demands.

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